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IMPLEMENTATION OF THE AGRARIAN REFORM OBJECT LAND PROGRAM IN FOREST AREA IN 2023 CASE STUDY IN JEMBAYAN VILLAGE, LOA KULU SUBDISTRICT

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Abstract

The research aims to determine the implementation of the Agrarian Reform Object Land Program and the role and support of stakeholders in the Implementation of the Agrarian Reform Object Land (TORA) Program in Jembayan Village, Loa Kulu sub-District, Kutai Kartanegara Regency, East Kalimantan Province, Indonesia. The research was carried out from September to November 2022 in Jembayan Village, Loa Kulu sub-District, Kutai Kartanegara Regency, East Kalimantan Province, Indonesia as the center for implementing administrative and technical activities of the TORA Program for East Kalimantan Province. The community population at the research location was 134 people and using the Slovin method a sample of 21 people was taken as respondents. The data collected consists of primary data obtained from observations and interviews with respondents and resource persons, and secondary data obtained from documentation in the form of archives and documents relevant to the research. This research uses qualitative research methods, the data analysis process is carried out through several stages, namely: data collection, data reduction, data presentation and analysis, and conclusion. The research results show that (1) TORA implementation is already underway, starting from the Inventory and Verification of Settlement of Land Tenure in Forest Areas (PPTKH) activities and Definitive Boundary Arrangement Activities, but to date, the final stage of distributing certificates from ATR/BPN has not been realized. The forest area allocation for providing TORA resources implemented by PPTKH is 30.05 hektare and is a function of the Permanent Production (HP) forest area. The implementation route for Definitive Boundary Arrangement activities in part of the Jembayan Village Permanent Production Forest Area was realized as long as 5,084.19 meters; and (2) the TORA program in Jembayan Village in terms of the benefits and support provided by stakeholders and the community is in the good category, namely 43.75% and 66.67%.

Keywords

Agrarian Reform Object Land Program, Forest Area.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Article 33 of the 1945 Constitution states that the earth's water and the natural resources contained therein are controlled by the state and fought for the greatest prosperity of the people. The prosperity of the people referred to here is in the sense of happiness, prosperity, and independence of the Indonesian people and a legal state that is independent, sovereign, just, and prosperous.

Control of land that provides benefits as a source of life is limited by corridors that are determined to be adhered to to prevent the emergence of social unrest between one another. This authority is owned by the state and is a reference in managing land and resources within and above it. The concept of natural resource management in Indonesia through Article 33 paragraph (3) of the 1945 Constitution also serves as a guideline in regulating the spatial planning of life (Manik, 2022).

Prolonged agrarian problems have become a social reality that is difficult to resolve, and unclear land ownership and control status have weakened the bargaining value of the community before the state or the private sector so that agrarian reform programs are urgently implemented (Kristianto, 2017). Furthermore, Sumarja and Akib (2018) stated that the background of the community in controlling the land within the forest area is very diverse. The unilateral designation of forest areas by the government in the past has been one of the triggering factors for conflicts that occurred in areas around forest areas. Ambarasti (2016) stated that the proliferation of non-forestry activities in forest areas often gives rise to various conflicts between sectors and between communities, government, and investors/private parties.

Therefore, it is necessary and important to have an agrarian reform program, namely as a basis for development that involves changes in function and also changes in the structure of control over land use and utilization to realize people's welfare and raise human dignity (Rachman 2012; Siscawati 2014; Luthfi 2018).

Agrarian Reform is a more equitable restructuring of the structure of control, ownership, use, and use of land through asset management and related access management for the welfare of the Indonesian people. The Government is committed to providing legal protection for people's rights as outlined in Presidential Regulation Number 88 2017 dated September 6 2017 concerning the Settlement of Land Tenure in Forest Areas (PPTKH).

The conversion of forest areas has been regulated in the Minister of Environment and Forestry Regulation Number 104 of 2015 P.51/Menlhk/Setjen/Kum.1/6/2016 concerning Procedures for Releasing Forest Areas that can be Converted into Production Forest. Apart from forestry activities, forest areas that can be developed are Convertible Production Forest (HPK) areas. HPK is a productive forest area that can be spatially set aside for development other than for forestry activities or can be used as replacement land for exchanging forest areas, especially HPK that is no longer productive, namely HPK whose land cover is dominated by non-forest land, including shrubs, land empty and mixed gardens.

The Agrarian Reform Program policy which is the mandate of the 1945 Law Article 33 paragraph 3, is concretely outlined in the community strengthening or empowerment program known as Nawacita, Nawacita is used as a reference for preparing the National Term Development Plan Book 2, in this document it is stated that the allocation of forest area land for social forestry activities covering an area of 12.7 million hectares, this is proof that the government is serious about improving the welfare of the community through social forestry programs.

Potential areas/land designated as community forests can be obtained from these unproductive HPK. According to the Decree of the Minister of Environment and Forestry Number SK. 180/Menlhk/Setjen/ Kum.1/4/2017 concerning Indicative Map of Forest Area Allocation for the provision of Land Resources for Agrarian Reform Objects (TORA). TORA sourced from HPK is unproductive, covering an area of around 2,169,960 hectares.

Apart from the social forestry program, Nawacita also explains the allocation of community business space which is outlined in a program popularly known as Land for TORA. TORA is defined as land controlled by the state or land that has been owned by the community for distribution or legalization (Presidential Regulation Number 86 of 2018 concerning Agrarian Reform).

In the TORA Program, 9 million hectares of land will be prepared to strengthen tenure rights and community property rights. The figure of 9 million hectares comes from non-forest areas or abandoned land covering an area of 4,5 million hectares. Another 4,5 million hectares comes from the

release of forest areas, including transmigration, 20% release of forest areas for plantations, and release of forest areas from production forests that can be converted.

TORA is one of the national development agendas that has been mandated in Presidential Regulation Number 2 of 2015 concerning the 2015-2019 National Medium-Term Development Plan (RPJMN). Furthermore, in Presidential Decree Number 45 of 2016 concerning the 2017 Government Work Plan where Agrarian Reform has been designated as one of the national priorities in development in Indonesia

Rationally, the TORA program will have an impact on improving the welfare of the community in Jembayan Village, Loa Kulu District, Kutai Kartanegara Regency, East Kalimantan Province. When people are assisted in the form of assets and access to production, naturally this assistance can encourage efforts to improve their standard of living. However, it is necessary to study further regarding the implementation process of the TORA program.

Based on the description above, it is necessary to carry out research to study further regarding what is the actual implementation process of the TORA program. Considering that the TORA program is closely related to the aim of improving community welfare, it is necessary to analyze the role and support that the government has provided the TORA program, especially in Jembayan Village.

The research aims to determine the implementation of the Agrarian Reform Object Land Program and the role and support of stakeholders in the Implementation of the TORA Program in Jembayan Village, Loa Kulu sub-District, Kutai Kartanegara Regency, East Kalimantan Province.

2. RESEARCH METHODS

2.1. Time and Location

The research was carried out from September to November 2022 in Jembayan Village, Loa Kulu sub-District, Kutai Kartanegara Regency, East Kalimantan Province, Indonesia as the center for implementing administrative and technical activities of the TORA Program for East Kalimantan Province.

2.2. Materials and Tools

The materials and tools used are Google Forms, questionnaire sheets, computers, cameras, voice recorders, and handphones.

2.3. Sampling

The community population at the research location was 134 people, to determine the number of data samples from community respondents using the Slovin method (Sugiyono, 2014) with the formula, namely:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N \cdot (d)^2}$$

Information: n = number of samples (respondents), N = total population, and d = specified precision (20%). Based on the calculation results, there were 21 respondents.

2.4. Data Collection

The data collected consists of primary data obtained from observations and interviews with respondents and informants, and secondary data is obtained from documentation in the form of archives and documents relevant to the research.

2.5. Instrument Scale Categorization

According to Azwar (2012), the purpose of categorization is to place individuals into separate groups in stages according to a continuum based on the attributes being measured. To make a categorization, the theoretical mean and population standard deviation units are needed. The following is the formula needed to create categorization in this research:

1. Maximum instrument score = number of questions × largest scale score
2. Minimum instrument score = number of questions × smallest scale score
3. Theoretical Mean (μ) = $1/2$ (maximum score + minimum score)
4. Population Standard Deviation (σ) = $1/6$ (maximum score + minimum score)

Based on the calculations above, each respondent will be classified into three categories as presented in Table 1 as follows:

Table 1. Three Category Formula.

Score Range	Category
$X < (\mu - 1.\sigma)$	Not good
$(\mu - 1.\sigma) \leq X \leq (\mu + 1.\sigma)$	Enough good
$X > (\mu + 1.\sigma)$	Good

Source: (Azwar, 2012)

Note: X = Total score for each respondent

2.6. Data Analysis

This research uses qualitative research methods, the data analysis process is carried out through several stages, namely: data collection, data reduction, data presentation and analysis, and conclusion.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Jembayan Village Profile

Jembayan Village is located in Loa Kulu sub-District, Kutai Kartanegara Regency, and borders other villages. To the north it borders Loa Kulu Kota Village, to the east it borders Bakungan Village, to the West it borders Jembayan Tengah Village and Jembayan Dalam Village and to the South, it borders Sungai Payang Village. The Administrative Map of Jembayan Village is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Administrative Map of Jembayan Village

Figure 1. Administrative Map of Jembayan Village

Based on data from Loa Kulu In Figures sub-District (Central Statistics Agency 2021), the Jembayan Village area has an area of ± 170.78 Km², a population of 10,353 people consisting of 5,357 men and 4,996 women (Source DKB Semester 2 2021). The majority of Jembayan Village residents are Muslim. The religions that developed in the Jembayan Village community are Islam, Protestantism, and Catholicism. In general, the livelihoods of Jembayan Village residents can be identified into several sectors, namely agriculture, plantations, services/trade, self-employment, civil servants, and others.

3.2 Results of Identification of Utilization Patterns and Area of PTKH

From the Land Control in Forest Area (PTKH) location in Jembayan Village covering an area of 33,17 hecates, the PTKH field inventory results obtained were only 30,05 hecates with a total of 91 plots of land. The identified land use utilization patterns include settlements covering an area of 12 hecates with a total of 94 plots, social facilities, and public facilities covering an area of 0,79 hecates totaling 4 plots, and cultivated land in the form of mixed gardens covering an area of 17,27 hecates with a total of 36 plots. There is an area of 3,12 hectares of the target area of the Inver PTKH location that is not requested in the form of roads, former Sumbermas mess halls, and empty land whose ownership is unknown. Juridical Studies

From the results of examining files and collecting information, it is known that the subjects of PTKH inventory applicants consist of individuals and agencies. Plots of land controlled by individuals are recognized and confirmed by the community and/or the Village Head. The results of the Inver PTKH subject study were that 131 plots covering an area of 29,53 hecates, applicants in Jembayan Village were individuals and 3 plots covering an area of 0,52 hecates were agencies.

Based on a study of the length of land tenure using Medium Resolution Satellite Image Interpretation Data, it is known that the information contained in the SP2FBT Document is that the duration of land tenure for PTKH objects is < 20 years for 14 parcels with an area of 2,03 hecates, land tenure > 20 years for 40 parcels with an area of 10 hecates and it is unknown how long the land has been controlled for 80 plots with an area of 18,03 hecates. Based on the interpretation of the 1998 Landsat 5 medium-resolution satellite image, it shows that the PTKH area in Jembayan Village has activities in the form of settlements and dry land farming mixed with bushes.

The results of document verification are carried out by visiting people who apply for PTKH. Document verification is carried out by looking at the completeness of the files proposed by the applicant, including SP2FBT, KTP, Proof of Rights, and completeness of other supporting files. From the proposal document, information can be taken regarding the name of the applicant subject and the relevant demographic information, location of the plot of land controlled, year of land control, and other information. The results of the verification of land tenure documents are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Verification of Land Tenure Documents in Jembayan Village.

No.	Subdistrict /Village	SP2FBT Document				Amount Field	Area (Ha)
		There is		There isn't any			
		Amount Field	Area (Ha)	Amount Field	Area (Ha)		
1	Loa Kulu						
a	Jembayan	64	15,51	70	14,54	134	30,05
Amount		64	15,51	70	14,54	134	30,05

From Table 2 it shows that in Jembayan Village there are plots of land at the target location of Inver PTKH covering an area of 30,05 hectares with 134 plots of land. There are 64 plots of land that have SP2FBT with an area of 15,51 hectares and 70 plots of land with an area of 14,54 hectares that do not have SP2FBT.

From the results of the physical verification of the proposed Jembayan Village land, it can be concluded that the land plots in Table 4 meet the criteria for utilization patterns in the form of settlements, social facilities, and public facilities as well as arable land and are in the TORA Revision IV Indicative map, the results can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3. Results of Field Survey of PTKH Objects.

Subdistrict	Village	Area of Target Location (Ha)	Extent of Application (Ha)	Amount Field	Indicative TORA Revision IV		Settlement		Social Facilities and Public Facilities		Arable Land	
					Inside	Outside	Amount Field	Area (Ha)	Amount Field	Area (Ha)	Amount Field	Area (Ha)
Loa Kulu	Jembayan	33,17	30,05	134	30,05	-	94	12,00	4	0,79	36	17,27

Source: Inver PTKH Field Survey in Bakungan Village, Loa Duri Ulu Village and Jembayan Village.

The results of field verification also show that the land plots requested are by the information contained in the SP2FBT. Regarding the boundaries between land parcels, the spatial data that has been carried out by desk analysis is adjusted to the actual measurement results in the field. The results of desk analysis and field verification are as follows:

1. Allocation of forest areas to provide TORA (Agrarian Reform Object Land) resources which carry out Inventory and Verification of Land Tenure in Forest Areas covering an area of 33,17 hectares and is the function of Permanent Production (HP) forest areas.
2. The identified land use utilization pattern includes settlements covering an area of 12 hectares with a total of 94 plots, social facilities, and public facilities covering an area of 0,79 hectares totaling 4 plots, and arable land in the form of mixed gardens covering an area of 17,27 hectares with a total of 36 plots. There is an area of 3,12 hectares of the target area of the Inver PTKH location which is not requested in the form of roads, former Sumbermas Mess, and empty land whose ownership is unknown.
3. Jembayan Village includes land tenure for less than 20 years totaling 14 plots with an area of 2,03 hectares, land tenure for more than 20 years totaling 40 plots with an area of 10 hectares and the length of land tenure is unknown for 80 plots with an area of 18,03 hectares. Based on the interpretation of the 1998 Landsat 5 medium-resolution satellite image, it shows that the PTKH area in Jembayan Village has activities in the form of settlements and dry land farming mixed with bushes.
4. The area of land ownership requested for Inver PTKH activities by Coordinating Ministerial Decree Number 3 of 2019 has a maximum limit of less than 5 hectares. Calculating the area of land ownership in Jembayan Village shows that all proposed plots have an area of less than 5 hectares.
5. There are differences in regional functions between Ministerial Decrees Environment and Forestry Number SK.8109/MENLHK-PKTL/KUH/PLA.2/11/2018 dated 23 November 2018 concerning Development Map of Confirmation of Forest Areas in East Kalimantan Province Until 2017. The results of the arrangement of regional boundaries for PTKH application areas in Villages Jembayan based on the BATB of the Jembayan River - Bakungan River Forest Group dated March 30, 2016, the PTKH inver area of 26,64 hectares is in the other use area.

3.2. Definitive Boundary Setting Activities

Definitive Boundary Arrangement Activities in some of the Jembayan River Permanent Production Forest Areas through changes in forest area boundaries for Settlement of Land Tenure in the Context of Forest Area Arrangement (PPTPKH) in Loa Janan and Loa Kulu sub-Districts, Kutai Kartanegara Regency, East Kalimantan Province.

The Sungai Jembayan Permanent Production Forest Group in Loa Janan and Loa Kulu sub-districts, Kutai Kartanegara Regency, has been appointed by the Decree of the Minister of Environment and Forestry Number SK.6628/MENLHK-PKTL/KUH/PLA.2/10/2021 dated 27

October 2021 concerning Map of Development of Confirmation of East Kalimantan Province Forest Areas up to 2020 which function as Permanent Production Forests and Other Use Areas.

In implementing the definitive boundary delineation activities for the Jembayan River Permanent Production Forest Area, technical personnel from the Samarinda Region IV Forest Area Stabilization and Environmental Management Center and UPTD KPHP Meratus were carried out. (Regional Technical Implementation Unit, Forest Management Unit)

The results of the implementation of the Definitive Boundaries of the Jembayan River Permanent Production Forest Area, which was realized as long as 5,084.19 meters, are outlined in the Minutes of Implementation of Definitive Boundary Arrangements in part of the Jembayan River Permanent Production Forest Area through changes in forest area boundaries for Settlement of Land Tenure in the Context of Forest Area Arrangement (PPTPKH) in Loa Janan and Loa Kulu sub-Districts, Kutai Kartanegara Regency.

3.2.1. Location

The location of the definitive boundaries of the Sungai Jembayan Permanent Production Forest Area, geographically located between $117^{\circ} 2' 12.05''$ E to $116^{\circ} 58' 22.81''$ E and $0^{\circ} 36' 58.23''$ South Latitude to $0^{\circ} 35' 39.88''$ LS. Based on the division of government administrative areas, the location of the Definitive Boundary Arrangement in part of the Jembayan River Permanent Production Forest Area through changes in forest area boundaries for settlement of Land Tenure in the Context of Forest Area Arrangement (PPTPKH) is in the Loa Janan and Loa Kulu sub-District, Kutai Kartanegara Regency. Meanwhile, based on the division of the Pemangkuan Forest area, the definitive boundary location is in the UPTD KPHP Meratus Area, East Kalimantan Provincial Forestry Service. The location of the definitive boundary route for the Sungai Jembayan Permanent Production Forest Area (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Layout of Definitive Boundary Route Locations

3.2.2. Forest Functions

Based on the Development Map of Confirmation of Forest Areas in East Kalimantan Province Up to 2020 (Attachment to the Decree of the Minister of Environment and Forestry Number SK.6628/MENLHK-PKTL/ KUH/PLA.2/10/2021 dated 27 October 2021), the location of the definitive boundaries is at The Sungai Jembayan Permanent Production Forest Area. Forest functions at the definitive boundary location of the Sungai Jembayan Permanent Production Forest Area are presented in the following figure 3.

3.2.3. State of Vegetation and Land Use

Based on the Land Use Development Map of East Kalimantan Province in 2021 which is the result of Landsat Image Interpretation 8 OLI/TIRS Coverage in 2021 (BPKH Region IV Samarinda,

2021), at the definitive boundary location of the Jembayan River Permanent Production Forest Area, there is land cover in the form of secondary forest and plantations, the condition of the vegetation is in the form of secondary forests and plantations. Land Cover Conditions at the definitive boundary location of the Jembayan River Permanent Production Forest Area are presented in Figure 4. SPOT-7 Image of Definitive Boundary Route Location.

Figure 4. SPOT-7 Image of Route Locations with Definitive Boundaries

3.2.4. Boundary Arrangement Results

The results of the implementation of the definitive boundary arrangement of the Jembayan River Permanent Production Forest (HP) area were realized as long as 2,136.69 meters. A summary of the results of measurements of definitive forest area boundaries and a comparison of plans with realization is presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Comparison of Plans and Realization of Boundary Arrangement

No.	Description	Plan (m)	Realization (m)	Difference (m)
1.	Limit Length	5.083,25	5.084,19	+ 0,94

Installation of boundary signs in the form of 51 (fifty-one) pieces of durable class I wooden boundary posts, 80 (eighty) boundary posts, and 5 (five) notice boards made of zinc plates.

3.3. Stakeholders and Society

The implementation of TORA involves many parties at each stage. These stages involve stakeholders as implementers of the TORA Program activity process and the community as recipients of the TORA program. Therefore, to determine the role and support of stakeholders according to what the community expects, researchers used a questionnaire method that was divided into 2 parties, namely a questionnaire for stakeholders and a questionnaire for the Jembayan Village community. The total number of respondents who took part in this research was 53 respondents, 32 respondents from stakeholders, and 21 respondents from the Jembayan Village community.

The results of the analysis of respondent questionnaire data from stakeholders related to the TORA program are as follows:

1. A total of 27 respondents (84%) chose to agree that the TORA Program is one of the priority programs of the East Kalimantan Provincial Government, 3 respondents (9%) chose neutral and 2 respondents (6%) chose to disagree, this was due to the respondents' perceptions regarding the Program TORA is not one of the priority programs.
2. A total of 25 respondents (78%) chose to agree that the TORA Program had been well socialized to the people of Jembayan Village and 7 respondents (22%) chose to be neutral, this was because the respondents were doubtful about this statement.
3. A total of 30 respondents (97%) chose to agree that the TORA Program is beneficial for communities around the forest, and 1 respondent (5%) chose neutral, this was because the respondent was doubtful about this statement.
4. A total of 31 respondents (100%) chose to agree with the statement that the TORA Program can improve the welfare of the community in Jembayan Village.
5. A total of 17 respondents (53%) chose to agree with the statement that the implementation of TORA in Jembayan Village was by the targets set by the Government, 12 respondents (38%) chose neutral, and 3 respondents (9%) chose to disagree because respondents thought that the implementation of TORA in Jembayan village was not by the targets set by the government.
6. A total of 24 respondents (75%) chose to agree with the statement that the implementation of TORA in Jembayan Village was by the work procedures that had been determined and 8 respondents (25%) chose neutral, this was because the respondents were doubtful about this statement.
7. A total of 16 respondents (50%) chose to agree with the statement that the implementation of TORA in Jembayan Village was in balance with the budget prepared, 12 respondents (38%) chose neutral, and 4 (12%) respondents chose to disagree with the statement on the implementation of TORA in the village Jembayan is balanced, this is because respondents think that the budget is not balanced.
8. A total of 25 respondents (78%) chose to agree with the statement that stakeholders had helped in achieving the TORA target process in Jembayan Village, 6 respondents (19%) chose neutral, and 1 respondent (3%) chose to disagree because the respondent thought that stakeholders have not helped achieve the TORA program target process.
9. A total of 26 respondents (81%) chose to agree with the statement that the stakeholder components that help implement TORA in Jembayan Village are by their respective roles and 6 respondents (19%) chose neutral, this was because the respondents were doubtful about the statement.
10. A total of 22 respondents (69%) chose to agree with the statement that the achievements of the TORA Program in Jembayan Village were satisfactory, while 10 respondents (31%) chose neutral, this was because respondents were doubtful about the statement that the achievements of the TORA program in Jembayan Village were satisfactory.

The results of the analysis of questionnaire data from community respondents related to the TORA program are as follows:

1. A total of 17 respondents (81%) agreed that the Government has carried out good outreach to the community regarding the ownership status of the land that you are currently using. Meanwhile 1 respondent chose neutral (5%), and 3 respondents (14%) chose not to agree, this was because the respondent did not participate in the socialization held by the government regarding the TORA program.
2. A total of 19 respondents (90%) chose to strongly agree with the statement that the TORA Program can help the ownership status of the land that you are currently using, while as many as 2 respondents (10%) chose to disagree, this is because the land that the respondents are currently using is not entered into the TORA indicative map.
3. A total of 14 respondents (67%) chose to agree with the statement that the TORA Program will help expand the agricultural land that you are currently working on, and 4 respondents (19%) chose neutral while 3 respondents (14%) chose to disagree with this statement because the land the respondents currently use is not included in the TORA indicators.

4. A total of 17 respondents (81%) chose to agree with the statement that the TORA Program was beneficial for you, while 4 respondents (19%) chose to disagree, this was because the respondents thought that the TORA program was less useful for the respondents.
5. A total of 15 respondents (71%) chose to agree that the land ownership status that you will have has an impact on the economic development of the family, 3 respondents (14%) chose to be neutral, while 3 respondents (14%) chose to disagree because the respondents assume that the respondent's economy is not helped by the TORA program.
6. A total of 20 respondents (95%) chose to strongly agree with the statement that you support the TORA program, while 1 respondent (5%) chose to be neutral, this was because the respondent was doubtful about this statement.
7. A total of 19 respondents (90%) chose to agree with the statement that support from the government has been implemented well in accelerating the pace of the TORA program, while 2 respondents (10%) chose to disagree, this is because the respondent's perception regarding support from the government has not been implemented properly. good at accelerating the pace of the TORA program.
8. A total of 17 respondents (81%) chose to agree with the statement that the government had done enough to help the smooth running of the TORA program in Jembayan Village, while 4 respondents (19%) chose to disagree with this statement because respondents thought that not all agencies were doing their jobs well in regarding the smooth running of the TORA Program.
9. A total of 15 respondents (71%) chose to agree with the statement that the TORA Program, do you agree that it will reduce conflicts between companies and communities in Jembayan Village, 4 respondents (19%) chose neutral, this is because respondents were doubtful about the statement Meanwhile, 2 respondents (10%) chose to disagree with this statement because the respondents thought that even with the TORA program, differences of opinion regarding territorial boundaries between companies and village communities could not be avoided.
10. A total of 21 respondents (100%) chose to agree with the statement that you have high hopes for the TORA program for the welfare of the community around Jembayan Village.

The results of calculating category status for calculating Stakeholder Category Norms and Community Category Norms are presented in Tables 5 and 6.

Table 5. Stakeholder Categorization

Categorization Norms	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Categorization
$X < 24,5$	5	15,63	Not Good
$24,5 \leq X < 30$	13	40,62	Enough good
$X > 30$	14	43,75	Good
Total	32	100%	

Source: Processed Primary Data

Table 6. Community Categorization

Categorization Norms	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Categorization
$X < 24,5$	1	4,76	Not good
$24,5 \leq X < 30$	14	66,67	Enough good
$X > 30$	6	28,57	Good
Total21	100		

Source: Processed Primary Data

Based on the results of the data analysis above, it shows that the TORA Program in Jembayan Village in terms of the benefits and support provided by stakeholders is in the good category, while from the community it is in the quite good category. Another similar research result reported by Menik (2022) was that the implementation of the TORA program in Sihaporas Village, Pematang Sidamanik District, Simalungun Regency, North Sumatra Province was less effective because obstacles were found in the communication factor dimension and the bureaucratic structure factor dimension in the form of transmission/distribution related to strategy (media and method) dissemination of poor information and fragmentation related to the division of duties and responsibilities of the Central and Regional Governments. The results of focus group discussions (FGD) indicate that the people of Sihaporas Village need increased knowledge and skills which are expected to increase the community's literacy level in line with improving the community's bargaining position with other parties. Furthermore, it was reported by Ihsan et al (2022) that the implementation of TORA in Sambabo Village, Ulumanda sub-District, Majene Regency is still not by community expectations due to the lack of socialization and communication carried out by the government resulting in differences in perceptions by the community and the government itself.

Procedures for Completion of Land Acquisition in Forest Areas, one of the activities of which is Inventory and Verification of Land Tenure in Forest Areas and Arrangement of Definitive Boundaries, is based on the PTKH Inver application proposal. The technical personnel carrying out TORA program activities in Jembayan village are: (1) Samarinda Region IV Forest Area Stabilization Center; (2) East Kalimantan Provincial Forestry Service; (3) Regional Office of the National Land Agency of East Kalimantan Province; (4) East Kalimantan Province Environmental Service; (5) East Kalimantan Province Public Works and Public Housing Service; (6) Kutai Kartanegara Regency Land and Spatial Planning Service; (7) Meratus Production Forest Management Unit Technical Implementation Unit; (8) Loa Kulu sub-District and (9) Jembayan Village. Furthermore, research results reported by Junarto and Djurdjani (2020) show that the implementation of TORA settlement can refer to the implementing regulations of the Forestry Law, including PP (Government Regulation) 44/2004, PP 24/2010, PP 104/2015, and Presidential Decree 88/2017 and Regulation of the Coordinating Minister for Economic Affairs Number 3 of 2018. Article 2 PP 104/2015 states that the allocation of forest areas and changes in their functions are carried out to meet the demands of national development dynamics and community aspirations. The resolution of forest land tenure problems in Banyuasin Regency, South Sumatra can be resolved using three schemes, namely boundary changes, social forestry, and resettlement.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1. Conclusion

Based on the research results, several conclusions can be drawn including the following:

1. TORA implementation is already underway, starting from the Inventory and Verification of Settlement of Land Tenure in Forest Areas (PPTKH) activities and Definitive Boundary Arrangement Activities, but to date, the final stage of distributing certificates from ATR/BPN has not been realized. The forest area allocation for providing TORA resources implemented by PPTKH is 30.05 Ha and is a function of the Permanent Production (HP) forest area. The route for implementing Definitive Boundary Arrangement activities in part of the Jembayan Village Permanent Production Forest Area has been realized as long as 5,084.19 meters.
2. The TORA program in Jembayan Village in terms of benefits and support provided by stakeholders and the community is in a good category, namely 43.75% and 66.67%.

4.2. Suggestions

Based on the results of the research and analysis that has been carried out, the researchers provide several suggestions for implementing the TORA Program in Jembayan Village in the future, including:

1. TORA management in Jembayan Village needs to continue to be supported by implemented policies and programs to support the TORA Program at the Site level.
2. The parties involved in the TORA Program in Jembayan Village can maintain policy stability until the final stage of completing this program, namely the distribution of certificates to the people of Jembayan Village.
3. It is necessary to carry out further research either specifically or regarding other methods of approach to aspects of TORA in Jembayan Village, to provide suggestions for future strengthening.

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REGULATION

- Presidential Regulation Number 88 of 2017 dated 6 September 2017 concerning Land in Forest Areas.
- Minister of Environment and Forestry Regulation Number 104 of 2015
P.51/Menlhk/Setjen/Kum.1/6/2016 concerning Procedures for Releasing Forest Areas that can be Converted into Production.
- Decree of the Minister of Environment and Forestry Number SK. 180/Menlhk/Setjen/ Kum.1/4/2017 concerning Indicative Map of Forest Area Allocation for the provision of Land Resources for Agrarian Reform Objects (TORA).